

Development of a Trowelable TPS Cork Material for Reusable Launch Vehicles

2nd International Conference on Flight Vehicles, Aerothermodynamics and Re-entry Missions & Engineering (FAR) 19-23 June 2022.
Heilbronn, Germany.

Sofia Paixão¹, João Carvalho¹, Christian Hantz²

¹Amorim Cork Composites (ACC),
Rua Comendador Américo Ferreira Amorim, 260, 4535-186 Mozelos VFR, Portugal

²German Aerospace Center (DLR), Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology
Supersonic and Hypersonic Technologies Department, Linder Hoehe, 51147 Cologne, Germany

Abstract

Thermal Protection Systems are key elements of space vehicles to keep the structural integrity of interior parts during the high heat loads reached during atmospheric reentry. Over the years, countless types of TPS were developed, with many different types of materials (since ablative to ceramics), all of them with the same goal: to insulate the vehicle surfaces without compromising aerodynamics or payloads of the final system. Thereby, TPS always should be lightweight, with low thermal conductivity and enough structure to withstand shear forces felt during spatial trajectories.

Amorim Cork Composites (ACC), as one of the leaders of cork industry, has been present in different aerospace projects, where cork performs an important role as thermal protection system. Due to all its attributes of being lightweight, with cellular structure that gives it very low thermal conductivity (around 0,05 W/m·K) and also by the whole possibilities of combining it with other materials, it allows the creation of composites with outstanding properties.

The work performed in the scope of the Retro Propulsion Assisted Landing Technologies (RETALT) project comprised the development of a new TPS, capable of being applied *in situ*, that fulfills the thermal requirements of the reentry trajectory studied for reusable launchers. The development was focused on a trowelable solution (that could be applied in the form of a paste, with a spatula) and to cure directly in the final structure, at room temperature. The final formulation gathers an epoxy matrix with cork granules and a set of additives that have been resulted from a selection process between different types of resins: phenolic, polymeric polyurethane and epoxy, together

with different types of additives: fire retardants, rheological and thermal adjuvants.

During the development, the formulations screening criteria was based on ease of application, followed by the characterization of thermal conductivity and thermal capacity measurements, as well as cone calorimeter tests to mainly observe the quality of the surface in terms of cracks and stiffness.

The selected material formulation was then tested in the L2K facilities at DLR, to evaluate its performance under high thermal loads (up to 600 kW/m²). During all the characterizations, the new material was compared with P50, a cork TPS material commercialized by ACC in the form of sheets.

The present document discloses the development process and results achieved along the project as well as the comparison with a TPS material already commercialized and currently used in spatial missions.

Keywords: TPS, *in situ*, Cork, RETALT, P50, TPS05, Trowelable.

1. Introduction

During the last years, spatial explorations have become more relevant, followed by a continuous increase of launches per year, by several companies around the world.

With that, developments in this sector have grown exponentially, not only in terms of structural materials, aerodynamics, and propellants, but also in terms of Thermal Protection Systems (TPS), which play a critical role to keep the thermal stability inside the launcher during atmospheric reentry and during other events of high thermal loads trough spatial trajectories.

Thermal Protection Systems serve as thermal barrier to decrease heat conduction from the outside of the launcher to the inside, ensuring that the mechanical and structural stability is kept, while some weight is added to the system. In this sense, several materials that can withstand these requirements are being produced and continuous research has been done by several companies to find the best solutions. [1]

Cork, the bark of the cork oak tree, gathers a set of properties that made it, since the beginning of the space age, a material of choice for such applications. Besides being a natural material, its cellular structure provides it a very low thermal conductivity as well as low density. These properties combined with high flexibility and relative low cost, have opened the door to the space industry, with innumerable cases of success. [2] [3]

These cork materials, and in particular the ones commercialized by Amorim Cork Composites, are produced in sheets, that are glued to the structure during the assembling process. Therefore, when complex geometries need to be covered, machining could be the only current option available to face this demand. [4]

In this sense, for RETALT project, the purpose was to achieve a TPS material, possible of being applied in situ to complex geometries, that kept the structural stability of the fairing, without compromising the vehicle's weight.

Several solutions were considered, based also on the current state of the art. Silicone, Epoxy and Phenolic are resins of choice, due to their high thermal resistance and excellent thermal stability, when combined with different fillers. They can achieve the best properties and comply with aerospace requirements. Also, ceramic composite materials (CMC) play an important role in aerospace industry, due to their higher thermal resistance and, consequently, reusability.

Regarding processing methods and final application technology, several approaches are already performed by TPS suppliers, as spray technique, impregnation, trowelability, agglomeration, among others. The technical procedures as well as the final application method needs to be carefully chosen, to ensure that it is perfectly suitable with cork properties. [5] [6]

In this way, the method chosen to perform this development was the trowelable technique, which allows the material to be applied directly in the surface and cured at room temperature, in a few hours. [7]

During the product development stage, all the characterizations are of high importance to verify the main features of the final material. A set of preliminary characterizations (Butane Torch, Cone Calorimeter and Thermal Analysis) were performed during the product development and more demanding and accurate ones at the end of the project (L2K).

2. Materials and Methods

The development phase was based on the research of different raw materials that could add value to the final solution, as well as the combination of them until reach a material possible of being applied by trowelability, with good thermal resistance. All processes were followed by a continuous optimization, not only in terms of formulation but also regarding the process techniques, to guarantee the homogeneity and isotropy of the material.

In Figure 1 is represented a scheme of the most important points of each phase of development, which are intimately related and dependent.

Figure 1 - Schematic representation of TPS design and manufacturing plan.

2.1. Formulation Design

Although the formulation design is always based in innumerable iterations with all the components, a defined path can be followed to reach the best solution, with the resin choice as priority, as it will be the matrix network of the material.

Resins with low viscosity but high solid contents are preferable for this type of application, once don't compromise the mixing processes and generally require less temperature to be fully cured. In this sense, although we tried phenolic and polyurethane resins, epoxy resin was chosen as the best option for the new TPS composite matrix.

The second point to evaluate is the cork type and amount to include in the formulation. At Amorim Cork Composites, different size ranges of cork granules are available, and for RETALT project, a range between 0,2 and 1 mm was tested. In general, the lower the cork size, the worse its flame behavior is. However, granules with dimensions higher than 1mm can compromise the mixing process and ending in poor homogeneity of the material.

Once the two main components were defined, the next point was the selection of fillers to improve thermal, fire and structural resistance of the material and finally the rheology modifier to add thixotropy and allow trowelability without any run out of the resin or the other components.

Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 list all the components tested during the formulation design.

Table 1 - Resin matrix options tested during formulation design.

Resin Matrix	Density (kg/m ³)	Viscosity (mPa·s)	Solid Content (%)	Gel Time h:min (Temp.)
MDI Polymeric Polyurethane	1180	1500	100	-
Phenolic Resin	1240	450-600	74	00:20 (130°C)
Epoxy (2 comp.)	1120	800	100	02:25 (20°C)

Table 2 - Cork sizes tested during formulation design.

Cork	Granules Size (mm)	Bulk Density (kg/m ³)
A	0,2 to 0,5	50 - 70
B	0,5 to 1	50 - 60

Table 3 - Fillers tested during formulation design.

Fillers	Main Objective	Format
Silicone Carbide	Thermal / Ablation Properties	Powder
Carbon Fibers	Thermal / Ablation / Structural Properties	Chopped fibers
Glass Fibers	Thermal / Ablation / Structural Properties	Fibers
Tabular Alumina	Thermal / Ablation Properties	Powder
Boric Acid	Thermal / Ablation Properties	Powder
Aluminum Hydroxide	Thermal / Ablation Properties	Powder
Phenolic Microspheres	Thermal / Ablation Properties	Microspheres
Glass Microspheres	Thermal / Ablation Properties	Microspheres
Thixotropic Agents	Rheology Adjustment	Powder

2.2. Production and Application Process

The production process was entirely made at lab scale, with a progressive upgrade of the mixing equipment, according with the process requirements of the formulation changes that occurred during the formulation design.

The equipment used in the very beginning of the project was a low-speed planetary mixer, that allowed to reach a homogeneous mix but with the disadvantage of taking too much time and able to produce only 100g per batch.

The need of having a perfect stoichiometry of epoxy resin both components, the introduction of carbon fibers and all the rheological adjustments needed to the formulation, required an equipment upgrade from the smaller planetary mixer for a laboratory high speed, intensive disperser. With this improvement, it was possible to increase the batch size and reduce the time necessary to reach a perfect homogeneous mixture. The drawback of this disperser was the heat build-up. Therefore, to avoid resin pre-curing, a slow hardener is necessary to add, as well as to have an ice water bath to cool down.

In Table 4 is described the full steps of the mixing process.

Table 4 - Process phases description.

	Components	Speed (rpm)	Time (min)
Phase 1	Epoxy A component	500	3
	Rheological additives		
Phase 2	Carbon fibers and remaining additives	500	10
Phase 3	Epoxy B component	300	2
Phase 4	Cork	300	2

When the mixture is finalized, and before resin gel time, it should be applied directly on a substrate, with a spatula, ensuring that the desired thickness is being kept. The material will be fully cured within 3 hours.

Depending on the substrate material, a pre-treatment could be required. For ceramic substrates, which have microporosities, adhesion is quite good without any additional treatment, but with metallic substrates like steel or aluminum, a sanding process followed by an epoxy primer should be done, before TPS application.

Due to the exothermic curing reaction of epoxy resin, it's not recommended to do layers thicker than 10mm. Therefore, to reach higher thicknesses, it should be done in different layers, and each new layer need to be applied during the gel time of the previous one, to ensure that is some tack to improve adhesion.

2.3. Characterization

Butane Torch

The first thermal characterization made to all materials produced was by a butane torch, at ACC laboratory. The main objective of this characterization was the analysis of the surface after being exposed to a flame, regarding its structure stability, and was a crucial point to decide which samples went forward to the next characterization step. In Table 5 are described the conditions of the test and in Figure 2 an example of a sample being tested, where TPS was applied in a ceramic substrate.

Table 5 - Butane Torch test conditions.

Samples Dimension (mm)	Flame Temp. (°C)	Flame Distance (mm)	Test Time (min)
100 x 100 x 10	1300 °C	50	4

Figure 2 - Butane Torch test.

Cone Calorimeter

After the trade-off performed by butane torch test, the best samples were tested at cone calorimeter, according to ISO-5660-1. This device can give several outputs as energy release during the burning process and CO₂/ CO concentrations over time. However, once again the main features analyzed after the test were surface appearance, intumescence, and char stiffness. In Table 6 are described the conditions of the test and in Figure 3 a picture representing the test.

Table 6 - Cone Calorimeter test conditions.

Samples Dimension (mm)	Flame Temp. (°C)	Flame Distance (mm)	Test Time (min)
100 x 100 x 10	~ 800 °C	75	4

Figure 3 - Cone Calorimeter test. [8]

Thermal Analysis

In parallel with cone calorimeter tests, different thermal properties were evaluated, to ensure that the material not only showed good performance when exposed to high temperatures but also how it behaves in terms of heat conduction and mass loss. Therefore, Specific Heat, Thermal Diffusivity, Thermal Conductivity and Thermal Expansion tests were performed according to [7] [9] [10].

Arc Heated Wind Tunnel (L2K)

The formulation that has shown the best result in all previous characterizations was tested in L2K arc heated wind tunnel at DLR, in parallel with P50, to validate the material in accordance with the RETALT trajectory conditions.

“L2K uses a Huels type arc heater with a maximum electrical power of 1.4 MW to energize the working gas to high enthalpy conditions and thus achieves cold wall heat flux rates up to 3 MW/m². Convergent-divergent nozzles can be mounted based on the required heat fluxes.

For the current test series, the L2K was used with the 100mm and 200mm nozzle configuration, depending on the design cold wall heat flux. Air was used as working gas for all tests.” [11]

In Figure 4 is represented the dimensions of the samples tested. For P50, the material was directly machined from a sheet of material. For TPS05, the material was applied in layers, until reach 40mm heigh, and then CNC machined to the final shape.

Figure 4 - L2K sample dimensions.

TPS05 and P50 were both tested at different heat fluxes and one sample of P50 and two samples of TPS05 exposed to cycle tests. In Table 7 it is represented the test conditions for each sample.

Table 7 - L2K test conditions for each sample. Adapted from [11].

Test id./Sample	Flow Condition (kW/m ²)	Test Duration (s)	Cycle Test
P50_1 (FC200)	200	180	N
P50_2 (FC400)	400	90	N
P50_3 (FC200)	200	180	N
P50_4 (FC200)	200	3*60	Y
P50_5 (FC600)	600	60	N
TPS05_1 (FC200)	200	180	N
TPS05_2 (FC400)	400	90	N
TPS05_3 (FC600)	600	60	N
TPS05_4 (FC200)	200	3*60	Y
TPS05_5 (FC400)	400	3*30	Y
TPS05_6 (FC200)	200	180	N

After the test, all the samples were submitted to weight and recession measurements.

3. Results and Discussion

Burning Tests (Butane Torch and Cone Calorimeter)

During the TPS design, all the formulations were burned with a butane torch as the first screening step [7] and the best solutions were exposed to a 75 kW/m² cone calorimeter test for 4 min. At this step, it was verified the potential of the formulation TPS05, due to the absence of cracks and the higher stiffness of the surface. This formulation comprises an epoxy matrix, filled with chopped carbon fibers, cork granules and other additives to improve fire resistance and rheology modifiers. In Figure 5 is represented both the initial and the final appearance of the material, before and after being exposed to cone calorimeter test.

Figure 5 - TPS05 before and after cone calorimeter test.

The next step was the thermal properties evaluation, namely specific heat, thermal conductivity, thermal expansion, and thermal gravimetric analysis.

Specific Heat

Table 8 - Specific Heat of TPS05 and P50 between 25° and 300°C. Adapted from [9]

Temperature (°C)	TPS05 (J/g·K)	P50 (J/g·K)
25	2,55	1,61
50	2,38	1,90
100	2,14	2,10
150	2,01	2,04
200	1,93	2,30
250	1,90	1,95
300	1,87	1,26

By observing Table 8, TPS05 has higher specific heat than P50 and shows less variations during the heating process. This effect can be related with higher structural stability of TPS05, due to the presence of carbon fibers and less amounts of cork, that turns it into a more chemical stable material in that temperature range. Also, both materials have a decrease in specific heat values at higher temperatures, probably due to the cork pyrolysis which starts at around 200-220°C.

Thermal Conductivity

Table 9 - Thermal Conductivity of TPS05 and P50 between 25°C and 250°C. Adapted from [9].

Temperature (°C)	TPS05 (W/m·K)	P50 (W/m·K)
25	0,25	0,06
50	0,17	0,07
100	0,14	0,07
150	0,13	0,07
200	0,13	0,08
250	0,12	0,07

Regarding thermal conductivity, represented in Table 9, TPS05 is, at 25°C, almost 4 times higher than P50. However, while P50 shows a slight increase as temperature rises, TPS05 significantly decreases its value, and, at 200°C, TPS05 thermal conductivity is just 1,5 times

higher than P50. This effect is also correlated with the composition and flame behavior of each material, as will be confirmed in L2K further results.

Thermal Expansion

Figure 6 - Thermal Expansion of TPS05 between -100° and 300°C. [10]

Figure 7 - Thermal Expansion of P50 between 0° and 500°C. [10]

Finally, the analysis of Figure 6 and Figure 7, of thermal expansion behavior of TPS05 and P50, it is possible to predict that TPS05 will show intumescence in the first moments, during the exposure to high heat conditions, while P50 will show a continuous recession during all the exposure period.

This effect is also related with the composition of both materials. While P50 is mainly composed by cork, which is consumed above 200°C, TPS05 has less amount of cork, a great amount of carbon, and some inorganic content, which turns it into a more stable material, with less mass loss.

Thermogravimetric Analysis

Figure 8 - Thermogravimetric Analysis of TPS05 and P50 in N₂ and N₂/O₂ atmosphere.

The thermogravimetric analysis, charted in Figure 8, show that P50 has higher mass consumption than TPS05, both in simple N₂ atmosphere and in N₂/O₂ atmosphere. Again, this is because P50 has higher percentage of cork on its composition and higher organic content.

L2K

Mass Loss

The final thermal characterization test that both materials were subjected was the L2K wind tunnel experiments, with all the information present in [11].

From there, it was possible to obtain information about the material behavior when exposed to 200, 400 and 600 kW/m², as well as during cycle tests.

The main aspects observed were mass loss, recession and/or intumescent rates and temperature reached at different depths of the probe.

Figure 9 - P50 Mass Loss percentage of each test condition. [11]

Figure 10 - TPS05 Mass Loss percentage of each test condition. [11]

The results present in Figure 9 and Figure 10 show that, for the same conditions, the new TPS (TPS05) has less mass loss than P50. Once again, this result was already foreseen during the thermal gravimetry analysis. Also, it can be observed, for both materials, that the mass loss percentage has higher values for lower heat fluxes, indicating that exposure time has more impact on the material behavior than the intensity of the heat flux applied.

Regarding the cycling tests, it is also possible to conclude that, for both materials, the mass loss is less representative when the material is 3 times exposed to heat flux (like 200 kw/m² during 3 x 60s), when compared to a single exposure (180s). From this observation it looks that the

char formed during ablation process in the first 60s cycle, gives a protective layer front to the probe along with a decrease of its thermal conductivity.

Also, comparing that the mass loss after 60s at 600kw/m² is lower than three times exposition at 200 kw/m², it was interesting, again, to see the impact of test time.

Recession/Intumescence

After each L2K test, measurements were made to evaluate recession and intumescence of each probe at each flow condition and time determined for the test.

All the test procedure and results are explained on [11] and a summary of the findings is charted in Figure 11 and Figure 13, together with images of the probes before and after the test, in Figure 12 and in Figure 14.

Figure 14 - Profile and surface of TPS05 probes before (left) and after (right) L2K test.

By observing Figure 11, P50 suffers recession when exposed to any heat flow condition. The corners of the probe get progressively reduced, due to the abrasion caused by the velocity of the plasma. The higher the total heat of the several test the more recession in the probes.

This result confirms that recession (and mass loss) is more related with time of exposure than with heat flow condition.

In Figure 13, the recession effect on TPS05 shows the opposite behavior of P50. Instead of recession, the material showed an expansion, that was larger for larger exposure times (smaller heat fluxes - 200 kW/m²).

For cyclic tests, performed at 200 kW/m² and 400 kW/m², it is noted an expansion in the first cycle, and recession in the remaining ones, more intense for 400 kW/m².

The step verified in the right section of the probe, for the ones exposed to 400 kW/m² was due to a piece broke off during the test, that was removed before scanning. This behavior was not expected and can be a result of porosity created during the production of the probe, that caused the fall of the material just in that point.

These results show that due to the great differences in the composition of both materials, their behavior in this sense is also totally different.

Temperature Measurements

All the probes, excepting the ones that underwent cycle tests, were instrumented with thermal sensors, at different thicknesses, to compute the temperatures reach in the interior during the tests. All the procedures and results are present at [11].

In Table 10 are represented the temperatures reached in the first sensor, positioned at 6mm from the surface exposed to the heat flux, for P50 and TPS05 at the three different conditions.

Figure 11 - Surface Recession of P50. [11]

Figure 12 - P50 probe before (left) and after (right) L2K test.

Figure 13 - Surface Recession of TPS05. [11]

Table 10 - Temperatures reached at T1 (6mm from surface) during L2K tests. Adapted from [12]

REF.	Flow Condition (kW/m ²)	Test Time (s)	T1 máx (°C)
P50_1	200	180	230
P50_2	400	90	105
P50_5	600	60	66
TPS05_1	200	180	170
TPS05_2	400	90	140
TPS05_3	600	60	100

By analyzing Table 10 - Temperatures reached at T1 (6mm from surface) during L2K tests. Adapted from Table 10 - Temperatures reached at T1 (6mm from surface) during L2K tests., it is possible to conclude that the exposure time has more impact on the temperature inside the probe than the heat flow condition. By comparing the two materials, it is also notable that P50 reached lower temperatures than TPS05, which is explained by its lower thermal conductivity, that compensates its larger recession. The only case where this effect was not verified was for 200 kW/m², where TPS05 reached a lower temperature inside than P50, in the same conditions. This effect can be related with the fact that, for higher exposure times (180s), the recession in P50 is highest while TPS05 shows an initial intumescent expansion, so its thickness increase compensates the higher thermal conductivity.

4. Conclusions

The development of TPS05, combining an epoxy matrix with cork granules, carbon fibers and thermal additives, led to a trowelable cork TPS solution, applicable in situ and cured at room temperature, with a set of properties summarized in Table 11, together with P50.

Table 11 - Thermal properties of TPS05 and P50.

Ref.	Density (kg/m ³)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Specific Heat (J/g K)	Thermal Diffusivity (mm ² /s)
TPS05	715	0,25	2,55	0,137
P50	460	0,062	1,61	0,084

When compared to P50, the new material has a higher density and thermal conductivity. However, it shows less mass loss and less recession when exposed to heat conditions. Although with low TRL, the new material

shows high potential to be used as an ablative TPS, with the advantage of been applied *in situ* in complex shapes.

Bibliography

- [1] G. Duffa, Ablative Thermal Protection Systems Modeling, A. E. Series, Ed., Reston: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Inc, 2013, pp. 1-13.
- [2] H. Pereira, Cork: Biology, Production and Uses, First Edition ed., Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2007, pp. 33-55, 232, 233.
- [3] Amorim, "amorimcorkcomposites.com," Copyright © Amorim Cork Composites S.A.. All rights reserved., [Online]. Available: <https://amorimcorkcomposites.com/en-us/materials-applications/aerospace/>. [Accessed 27 05 2022].
- [4] J.-M. Bouilly, F. Bonnefond, L. Dariol, P. Jullien and L. Frédéric, "Ablative thermal protection systems for entry in Mars atmosphere. A presentation of materials solutions and testing capabilities," in *4th International Planetary Probe Workshop*, Pasadena, California, 2006.
- [5] S. E. Headrick and R. L. Hill, "Trowelable Ablative Coating Composition and Method of Use". Patent US4772495A, 6 June 1989.
- [6] W. G. Simpson, M. H. Sharpe and W. E. Hill, "Sprayable lightweight ablative coating". Patent 5,064,868, 12 November 1991.
- [7] S. Paixão, J. Carvalho, C. Peixoto and M. Reinas, "RETALT_TPS Design and Manufacturing," *CEAS Space Journal*, pp. 1 - 14, 2021.
- [8] CSIRO, CSIRO - Science, 30 10 2000. [Online]. Available: <http://www.scienceimage.csiro.au/pages/about/>. [Accessed 30 05 2022].
- [9] N. Marques, "Thermal Conductivity," ISQ, 2020.
- [10] N. Marques, "Thermal Expansion Coefficient," ISQ, 2020.
- [11] C. Hantz, A. Marwege, S. Paixão, L. Celotti and M. Wisniewska, "Thermal characterization of cork and ceramics based TPS in DLR Arc-heated wind tunnel L2K," in *2nd International Conference on Flight Vehicles, Aerothermodynamics and Re-entry Missions and Engineering (FAR)*, Heilbronn, 2022.
- [12] C. Hantz and A. Marwege, "Thermal Tests on RETALT Cork and Ceramic Samples, L2K," 2022.

